

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF CHICKENPOX AMONG CHILDREN IN THE KHAREZM REGION

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Annotation

Varicella is not a harmless disease; a certain percentage of various complications are recorded, including those requiring subsequent hospitalization. Moreover, this is observed in children under the age of 15 years with normal immunity. With age, the risk of complications and mortality can increase up to 50%, provided that the sick adult has not had varicella before or has not been vaccinated. Often, secondary skin infections, pneumonia, varicella encephalitis, cerebellar ataxia, lesion of the facial nerve, and eye damage are recorded as complications.

Keywords

Varicella, rash, immunity, temperature, skin, infection.

Chickenpox is an extremely contagious acute infectious disease. The causative agent of chickenpox - a DNA-containing virus - causes the development of two diseases: chickenpox at the first contact with the virus and shingles during the reactivation of the virus in the body of a previously ill person [7]. The causative agent of chickenpox is the Varicella zoster virus, which belongs to the family of herpetic viruses. In the external environment, the virus is unstable and quickly dies [1]. The only source of infection is a person. The susceptibility to chickenpox is very high. The entrance gate of infection is the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract. Viruses are released in large quantities when sneezing, coughing, talking. It is also possible to transmit the virus from the mother to the fetus during pregnancy [5]. Despite the fact that the most vulnerable category in terms of the incidence of chickenpox are mostly children of preschool age, adults can also get sick [2]. At the same time, do not forget that the disease in adults is fraught with the development of severe complications, the most common of which is pneumonia. The urgency of the problem of chickenpox is determined by the high contagiousness, the wide spread of this disease, the risk of complications, especially in adults [3;4].

The purpose of the study: Analysis of epidemiological features of chickenpox among children in the Khorezm region.

Materials and methods of research: In order to study the symptoms of the clinical manifestation of chickenpox in modern conditions, we have analyzed the archival case histories of 46 children with chickenpox under 1 year old who were hospitalized in the regional clinical infectious diseases hospital of Urgench in the period from 2015 to 2017.

Chickenpox is an acute, highly contagious infectious disease accompanied by an increase in body temperature and the appearance of a characteristic spotty – bubble rash on the surface of the skin and mucous membranes. The susceptibility to chickenpox is exceptionally high – almost 100%. Children under the age of 7 and of primary school age are more susceptible to the disease. Children of the first 2-3 months of life and older than 10 years, as well as adults, rarely suffer from chickenpox, since specific antibodies are present in their body. Chickenpox in children can also occur in newborns due to the lack of immunity in the mother. A high number of cases of chickenpox occur in the cold season – in autumn and winter. In summer, the incidence is significantly reduced. A characteristic feature of chickenpox is the occurrence of epidemic outbreaks, most often in children's organized collectives (in preschool organizations). After the child suffers from this disease, he forms a stable immunity. Repeated diseases occur very rarely (about 3% of cases).

In 10-20% of those who have been ill, the chickenpox virus remains in the nerve ganglia for life and subsequently causes another disease that can manifest itself at an older age - shingles or herpes zoster. Herpes zoster is characterized by prolonged and excruciating neuralgic pain, and also has a number of complications in the form of lesions of the nervous system and internal organs – paralysis, visual impairment. People with herpes zoster can be a source of infection with chickenpox.

Chickenpox can also cause damage to the fetus or newborn when a woman has chickenpox in the first 20 weeks of pregnancy or in the last days before childbirth. Vaccination against chickenpox in children and adults provides an opportunity to prevent these consequences. There is a small risk of post-vaccination infection in people with severe immunodeficiency (hematology, etc.), but in any case, vaccination of these people against chickenpox in developed countries is carried out as a standard procedure for the prevention of severe chickenpox.

Research results: The main group of sick children with chickenpox were children older than 3 months – 35 (76.0%). The specific weight of chickenpox in the group of children under 3 months was 11 patients (24%), from 3 to 6 months – 12 patients (26%). In the group of children from 6 to 9 months, 10 patients (21.7) and from 9 months to 1 year – 13 patients (28.3%).

The frequency of chickenpox did not depend on the sex of the sick children: so there were 25 girls (54%), 21 boys (46%). Of the 46 children with chickenpox, only 35 (76.0%) had contact with chickenpox patients. On the first day of the disease, 20 (43.5%) children were admitted, on the 2nd day – 12 (26.0%), on the 3rd day – 8 (17.4%) children. After 3 days from the onset of the disease, only 6 children were admitted, which amounted to 13.0% of the number of cases.

In 30 (65.2%) patients the body temperature rose to 38 ° C, in 11 (23.9%) – to 39 ° C and in 5 (10.9%) the body temperature was above 39 °C. Mild form of the disease was registered in 78% of cases, moderate in 18% and severe in 4%. Polymorphic vesicular rash was observed in all patients. The course of the disease was undulating and it was for this reason that rashes appeared at intervals of up to several times.

Conclusions. Thus, it should be noted that in recent years in practice there has been an increase in the incidence of chickenpox in children under 1 year old. The clinical picture of chickenpox retains its typical features. In infants and young children, a mild form of the disease prevails.

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